

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

(e)

(f)

(g)

(h)

(i)

(j)

(k)

(l)

(m)

(n)

(o)

(p)

(q)

Supplementary Figure S2. Differences between weight classes in all parameters, (a)-(c) anthropometrics, (d) – (i) physical fitness tests, (j) concentration score, (k) – (q) health-related Quality of Life (HRQOL) sub-scales